

Studies on Phototropism in Solution.

Part II.

The Optical Activity as an Aid in the Study of Phototropy.

BY

BAWA KABTAR SINGH.

In Part I of this series of investigations (J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1921, 43, 333), the author described some new cases of phototropism which exhibit the phenomenon in solution only. These were α -naphthylaminocamphor, *m*-phenylenebisaminocamphor and *ar*-tetrahydro- α -naphthylaminocamphor when dissolved in chloroform. With one possible exception, namely, di-9-hydroxy-phenyl-anthryl-10-amine (Foresti, *Atti R. accad. Lincei*, 1914, (V), 23, 270) phototropy had not previously been observed except in the case of solids.

The object of the present paper is to describe some experiments which have been carried out with one of these optically active phototropic substances, namely, α -naphthyl-aminocamphor, in which the phototropic change has been followed by means of a polarimeter.

The term phototropism was originally applied to reversible isomeric changes in solid substances produced by light and accompanied by change of colour. Since the above discovery by the author (*loc. cit.*), no such limitation with regard to the state of aggregation of the substance is recognised, and the term is equally applied to include all isomeric changes in substances in solution induced by light and accompanied by change of colour.

Phototropism in the Solid State.

The phenomenon was originally noticed by Marckwald (*Zeitsch. Physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 30, 140) in the case of

the yellow hydrochloride of quinoquinoline which changes to green in light, and reverts to the original colour in the dark and in that of β -tetrachloro- α -ketonaphthalene, which is colourless in the dark, and reddish violet in the light. Senier and Shepherd (T., 1909, 95, 441, 1943), found in salicylidene *m*-toluidine, a remarkable photo-reactive substance. It is pale yellow in colour. On exposure to sunlight, it changes to deep orange, and reverts to its original colour when placed in the dark. The change brought about by light is much faster than the reverse change. The spectroscopic evidence shows that the change from the pale-coloured to the dark-coloured modification is due to the activity of the light rays of high refrangibility. The change does not take place in solution, in which case only the pale-coloured modification appears to exist. The phenomenon exhibited by salicylidene *m*-toluidine thus opened a new and interesting field of research, and Senier and Shepherd (*loc. cit.*), examined a number of Schiff's bases, out of which only a few turned out to be phototropic, though most of them were thermotropic. Those which exhibit phototropy are derived from salicylaldehyde, in which the substituents are in the ortho position. The substitution of hydroxyl by methoxyl destroys the phototropic effect entirely.

The differences in colour produced by light in phototropic substances undoubtedly depend on some kind of isomeric change. The molecules of solids are far more complex than those of liquids and gases, and in fact their molecular magnitude is practically unknown. They may be regarded as aggregates of ordinary gaseous molecules. Consequently Senier and Shepherd (*loc. cit.*) suggest that the phototropic behaviour of solids is not due to intramolecular change, but to extramolecular rearrangement of simple molecules into molecular aggregates.

Phototropism in Solution.

The optically active substances which exhibit remarkable phototropic reactions in solution are very suitable for studying the course of the change, which can be conveniently followed by means of rotatory power determination. The yellow sodium light is unsuitable as it cannot pass through the green solution obtained after exposure to sunlight. The mercury green light ($\lambda=5461$) is easily transmitted through the solution for a considerable depth of colour, and is therefore employed in following the change. In this paper, a preliminary account of some experiments carried out with α -naphthylaminocamphor is given. A more detailed study of the phenomenon with this and other compounds is reserved for a future communication.

The following polarimetric experiment made with a chloroform solution of α -naphthylaminocamphor shows that the intensity of the colour and the rotatory power of the solution increase with the time of exposure to direct sunlight, and that the reverse change in the dark takes place much more slowly.

0.726 gram of the substance made up to 100 ccs. gave the following values for rotatory power at 30°:—

Time of exposure to—

(a) light (minutes)			[α]5461
0	126.0
1	137.0
2	149.0
3	160.3
4	168.5
5	173.0
6	186.6
7	too dark to read.
(b) dark (hours)			
23	168.0

A second polarimetric experiment illustrates the

influence of sodium ethoxide on the phototropic change. The addition of a drop of an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide to a chloroform solution of α -naphthylaminocamphor entirely inhibits the phototropic change. The solution to which no sodium ethoxide is added, undergoes the usual photo-reaction.

0.73 gram made up to 100c.cs. gave the following results:—

	[α]5461 With sodium ethoxide	[α]5461 Without sodium ethoxide
(a) before exposure	110°	137°
(b) 2 days in dark followed by 5 minutes' exposure to sunlight...	113	170

The photo-reaction of α -naphthylaminocamphor in chloroform solution is dependent on the nature of the light employed. Under the influence of light waves of high refrangibility (blue rays), the colourless chloroform solution changes to green, and when removed from that influence it returns to its original colour. The orange or red light is practically without any effect.

The phototropic change of α -naphthylaminocamphor also depends on the nature of the solvent, in which it is dissolved. The effect is only noticed in chloroform, in which it dissolves as a colourless solution, and it remains so if it is kept in the dark, but on exposure to sunlight the colour becomes deep bottle green within a minute. In the dark the green colour vanishes completely in about 24 hours. In other solvents, namely, acetone, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, ether, petroleum ether, and ethyl acetate, the colour changes which take place on exposure to sunlight, are comparatively very slow and are irreversible. The colour developed in these cases varies from light yellow to deep yellow and the time required for the colour to appear varies from half-an-hour to five hours. It therefore seems that chloroform is the

only solvent in which the reversible photo-reaction can be observed.

These results run parallel with the colour reactions which α -naphthylaminocamphor dissolved in the same solvents gives with ferric chloride. With the chloroform solution of the substance, ferric chloride gives a port wine colour before exposure to light and reddish brown colour after exposure; it thus indicates the presence of enol modification in it. Solutions in ethyl alcohol and ethyl acetate (in which the reversible photo-reaction is not observed) do not produce any colour, characteristic of hydroxy compounds, with ferric chloride both before and after exposure to light. This shows that in these solvents, the substance exists in the keto form only. It therefore, follows that only the chloroform solution of the substance is an equilibrium mixture of the keto-enol modifications of the following type:—

The addition of sodium ethoxide to the chloroform solution shifts the above equilibrium so that it contains the enol modification only. In this case also the solution does not undergo the phototropic change. It would therefore, appear that for the occurrence of the phototropic change both the keto and enol modifications should be present together in solution.

The keto modification $C_9H_{11} < \begin{array}{l} \text{CH} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot C_{10}H_7 \\ | \\ \text{C}:\text{O} \end{array}$, represents the substance as a mono-aryl derivative of aminocamphor. It ought, therefore, to be colourless.

The enol modification $C_9H_{11} < \begin{array}{l} \text{C} \cdot \text{NH} \cdot C_{10}H_7 \\ || \\ \text{C}:\text{OH} \end{array}$, should also be colourless, as the chloroform solution of the substance in the presence of sodium ethoxide is colourless.

In the former paper (*loc. cit.*) the author had suggested that the green colour of the solution may be due to the enol modification. This view seems to be now disproved by the foregoing arguments.

The phototropic change of α -naphthylaminocamphor in chloroform is due, therefore, not to the change of the keto to the enol form. It occurs only when both the modifications are present together in solution and is accompanied by the formation of a green substance, and by a marked increase in the rotatory power of the solution.

It may be tentatively suggested that the phototropic change is due to the mutual interaction of keto and enol modifications of the substance with the production of a compound of the "quinhydrone" type:—

The colour of such a compound could be explained in the same way by which Willstätter (Ber., 1908, 41, 1458, 3245) explained the colour of quinhydrones.

The non-occurrence of the phototropic change in solvents in which no enolisation takes place, as well as the similar influence of sodium ethoxide in which case only the enol modification exists, can both be explained on this hypothesis. The above explanation of the phototropic change is only provisional, and is to be tested by further experiments.

THE CHEMICAL LABORATORY,

RAVENSHAW COLLEGE, CUTTACK, ORISSA.

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